

COAR NARRATIVE SERIES

Safeguarding Digital Sovereignty through Local Stewardship and Preservation

Confederation of Open Access Repositories

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The accelerating trend of digital sovereignty

Over the past century, the scholarly communications ecosystem has shifted from a landscape of many small, independent journals serving discrete scholarly communities to one dominated by a handful of large commercial publishers, each maintaining catalogues of thousands of journals, and continuing to acquire competitors and associated services (Larivière et al., 2015). The result is a quasi-monopolistic market in which five companies (based mainly in the US and Europe) now control the majority of the world's scholarly output, and in which scholarly communities have largely lost governance and influence over the platforms and infrastructure on which they depend (Fyfe et al., 2017). Compounding this, commercial publishers tend to prioritise English-language content and topics of interest to Western research communities, often at the expense of locally relevant scholarship.

For these reasons, and others, many countries are reassessing how and where they host and preserve their research outputs (Jansen et al., 2023). This shift mirrors a broader trend in the geopolitical landscape, in which nations are increasingly investing in sovereign digital infrastructure, not only for research but as an alternative to the large commercial platforms on which their populations have grown dependent.

Such concerns extend far beyond publications. The datasets, analytical tools, and platforms on which researchers depend often rely on external digital infrastructures that are hosted and governed outside the regions that produce and use them (Ruckstuhl, 2022; Gu, 2023). As research data becomes increasingly valuable, especially as raw material for artificial intelligence systems (Digital Science et al., 2025), the location where it is stored and who governs its use has implications that extend far beyond the research community.

The urgency of these sovereignty efforts becomes clear when real-world disruptions strike. When the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) faced drastic funding cuts in early 2025, researchers across multiple countries suddenly risked losing access to datasets they had helped create. The episode illustrated a structural vulnerability: dependence on foreign platforms can convert a distant political decision into an immediate local crisis with no warning and no remedy.

In the research domain, the push for data sovereignty has been especially prominent in Latin America and Africa, which have long experienced extractive relationships with Western science. Researchers from wealthier countries have routinely come to these regions to conduct studies and then return home with the resulting outputs, leaving little behind.

A recent Brazilian publication captures many of the structural dimensions of this problem:

"When researchers in the Global South deposit their data in repositories controlled by foreign companies, use proprietary analytical platforms, or depend on cloud infrastructures located in other countries, they are, to some extent, ceding sovereignty over a strategic resource" (da Silva, 2025)

Responses to this dynamic have taken root across both regions. For over three decades, Latin America has made significant investments in local scholarly infrastructure, producing two major publishing and hosting platforms (Redalyc and SciELO) as well as regional discovery and indexing services. It should be noted that in addition to securing local sovereignty, these infrastructures provide support for Spanish and Portuguese language publications, the two main languages of Latin America. Africa has pursued similar goals, though in a less coordinated manner, through initiatives such as African Journals Online and WACREN's LIBSENSE programme, which aim to ensure that research produced on the continent is managed and preserved locally (Abbot, 2025; Abbott et al., 2025).

These conversations are now taking place in other regions as well. China, which has become the world's most prolific producer of scientific publications (Pisani et al., 2025), has predominantly published papers in journals hosted outside of the country, with only a very small percentage (around 5%) published in Chinese-owned journals (Yang & Huang, 2025). To address this imbalance, China has recently stated its intention to develop its domestic infrastructure for publishing and managing its research outputs (Owens, 2024; Yang & Huang, 2025). In Canada, with a focus on securing local copies, the major federal research funding agencies have proposed an open access policy that would require all peer-reviewed articles arising from publicly funded research to be deposited in a Canadian institutional repository upon publication, irrespective of availability on a publisher's platform (Canadian Institutes of Health Research et al., 2025). The policy is explicitly aimed at ensuring that there are copies of all Canadian funded research articles preserved in Canada and available to the Canadian public.

Europe is also grappling with similar questions about control over critical research infrastructure. The European Parliament's Panel for the Future of Science and Technology recently hosted a discussion on data sovereignty in research to warn about the risk that dependence on external and commercial databases could pose strategic vulnerabilities for academic freedom, innovation, and research continuity (European Parliament, 2025). Subsequently, the EOSC Steering Board published an opinion paper recommending that Europe strengthen its capacity to govern and safeguard research outputs by investing in federated sovereign infrastructure (European Commission, 2025). These concerns are being formalised through various laws and statutes in the European

Union, such as the Digital Services Act (2022), as well as various national regulations and increased investments in local infrastructures.

These digital sovereignty initiatives vary in form and ambition, but they share a common concern: if the systems that store and provide access to a nation's research outputs are hosted and governed elsewhere, what happens when terms of access change, political relationships deteriorate, or services are simply discontinued?

The role of repositories in realising digital sovereignty

Digital sovereignty in research refers to the capacity of researchers, institutions, and nations to control, access, and preserve their scholarly outputs without dependence on commercial intermediaries or foreign jurisdictions. While it is extremely difficult for many countries to achieve full technological independence, since the underlying digital infrastructure is often globally distributed and beyond any single entity's control, they can control where their outputs are stored. This is precisely the function repositories serve: to ensure that valuable national assets produced through research are held within a trusted, locally-governed infrastructure.

Institutional repositories have been part of the scholarly landscape for more than two decades, with the first open-source platforms emerging in the early 2000s alongside the Budapest Open Access Initiative, which identified repositories as critical infrastructure for making research freely available (Budapest Open Access Initiative, 2002; Rothfritz et al., 2025). Since then, repositories have expanded across every region of the world, forming a broad, distributed network of predominantly institutionally hosted infrastructures. For countries pursuing greater research sovereignty, they are an important tool that can be leveraged to support these aims.

In the context of digital sovereignty, the preservation function of repositories takes on particular significance. Repositories are purpose-built to manage research outputs under the stewardship of the institutions and communities that produced them, offering a considerably more secure and accountable alternative to entrusting a nation's research heritage to foreign commercial entities. Moreover, the distributed nature of the repository network means that this custody does not depend on any single institution or platform.

While one enticing solution to the national management of research outputs is to consolidate everything into a single centralised national platform, this type of concentration carries with it the inherent risk of a single point of failure and a one-size-fits-all architecture that is unlikely to serve the varied needs of different disciplines, institutions, and research communities. Repository networks offer a fundamentally different model: federated rather than centralised, with each node maintaining its own governance, scope, and functionality, while remaining connected to

national and global networks through shared protocols and standards. Sovereignty, in this framing, does not require uniformity, but rather interoperability.

Interoperability for resilience and global visibility

A legitimate concern with the trend toward digital sovereignty is that locally built infrastructures will be inaccessible beyond national borders or because they have not been developed with international standards in mind, contributing to greater fragmentation of the global knowledge commons (Silva, 2025). However, sovereignty pursued through isolation is self-defeating: if countries and institutions retreat into walled gardens, the connectivity on which international scholarship depends will be compromised. International interoperability is therefore a foundational requirement for these national and institutional services. It is the mechanism which allows nations to maintain local control while also contributing to the global information system.

Interoperability is already a core design principle built into repository architecture. Most of the widely used platforms support common APIs and protocols that enable content harvesting and discoverability, such as OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting). But this basic technical compatibility alone is insufficient. For a repository to be interoperable and discoverable beyond its local or national context, it must satisfy a layered set of requirements: multilingual tagging, open licensing, high-quality metadata supported by persistent identifiers (PIDs), and emerging protocols and APIs that enable linking (COAR Notify) and reliable machine access. These are critical factors for ensuring that a repository's resources can be visible beyond direct users of the platform by being indexed, harvested, and crawled by aggregators and search engines.

Ramping up repositories to meet the challenge

The contribution of repositories to digital sovereignty is well established, yet a number of structural and operational improvements would enhance their effectiveness in this regard. Preservation capacity, for example, may be among the most significant gaps. Digital preservation encompasses the active, ongoing management of digital objects against bitrot, format obsolescence, and institutional discontinuity, involving technically complex, resource-intensive processes. Most open access repositories do address some of the requirements related to digital preservation, such as maintaining backup copies and monitoring file integrity; however, few are able to satisfy the most comprehensive preservation frameworks, such as OAIS (Open Archival Information System), which sets the professional standard for long-term archival management.

Most repositories fall short of robust digital preservation requirements for a combination of structural, technical, and governance reasons. Funding is perhaps the most fundamental constraint: preservation demands ongoing investment in storage,

migration, and specialist staffing that many repositories cannot sustain (Barrueco & Termens, 2020). Compounding this, many repository platforms were designed primarily for access and discovery rather than long-term stewardship, and lack the underlying infrastructure for fixity checking, format migration, or geographically distributed redundant storage that preservation standards require (Rieger et al., 2022). At the governance level, many repositories operate without formal preservation policies, leaving institutional commitment informal and vulnerable to shifts in leadership or priorities (Dowding, 2016).

Given these challenges, a more realistic approach for rigorous preservation of research outputs in repositories could involve the integration of institutional repositories with more comprehensive national-level preservation initiatives that provide the necessary expertise and resources required for the network of repositories. The current deficiencies in the digital preservation capacities of repositories, however, do not diminish the importance of their role in providing a foundational and irreplaceable layer of local stewardship for an institution's and a country's research assets.

Interoperability also remains a persistent challenge. Many repositories have yet to fully adopt the technical and metadata practices needed to interconnect with other systems, a problem spanning both infrastructure and institutional capacity (Rothfritz et al., 2025). Low resources and understaffing lead to inconsistent metadata practices across repositories, undermining the ability of aggregators and search engines to index their content reliably. This is not a new problem: as far back as 2010, Park and Tosaka found that metadata accuracy and consistency were considered the most important quality metrics and yet the hardest to maintain, a finding that, more than a decade later, remains largely unresolved.

One of the most persistent obstacles to the optimisation of repository operations is the combination of understaffing and ageing software infrastructure. A 2025 systematic review found that 82% of studies identified professionalisation as a significant problem, with shortages of qualified personnel documented across repositories in countries spanning every region (Shearer et al., 2023; Rothfritz et al., 2025; Macgregor & Davidson, 2026). The consequences are visible in the infrastructure itself: outdated systems, inactive interfaces, and repositories that have fallen into disrepair.

The fragility of many repositories reflects the low priority level libraries and institutions have traditionally assigned to their operations. Repositories have often occupied a marginal position within their institution, a situation that reflects a confluence of structural, cultural, and financial factors. In most institutions, repositories were established as compliance mechanisms for open access policies, rather than as strategically valued infrastructure in their own right (Rothfritz et al., 2026). As a result, they have tended to receive the minimum investment necessary to remain operational, with staffing, technical development, and outreach frequently treated as discretionary

rather than essential expenditure. This positioning is reinforced by the prevailing reward structures of academic institutions, which have historically privileged research outputs – publications, grants, and citations – over the infrastructure that supports their management and dissemination (Hahn, 2008). The cumulative effect is a chronic pattern of under-investment that has left many repositories technically outdated, insufficiently staffed, and poorly integrated into the broader research and publishing ecosystem. These challenges will have to be addressed as we ramp up repositories to meet the growing demands for digital sovereignty.

Conclusion

The consolidation of scholarly infrastructure in the hands of a small number of commercial publishers and foreign platforms has created dependencies that many countries are only now beginning to fully reckon with. As the geopolitical landscape shifts and the fragility of those dependencies becomes harder to ignore, the question of who controls the systems that store, govern, and provide access to national research outputs is moving from a niche concern to a matter of strategic priority.

Repositories are not a new answer to this challenge. They have been part of the scholarly landscape for more than two decades, quietly performing functions that are only now being recognised as geopolitically significant. Their distributed, institution-governed architecture makes them uniquely well-suited to a federated model of sovereignty: one that preserves local control without sacrificing global connectivity, and that can be adapted to the varied needs of different disciplines, languages, and research traditions. The infrastructure, in other words, already exists. What has been lacking is the recognition of its strategic value and the investment needed to fulfil its potential.

That investment is overdue. Chronic understaffing, ageing systems, inconsistent metadata practices, and limited preservation capacity are not inherent weaknesses of the repository model; they are the accumulated consequences of treating repositories as a background utility rather than a critical national asset. Addressing them will require sustained funding, shared infrastructure, coordinated policy, and a willingness to treat repository operations with the same seriousness that governments are now beginning to apply to digital sovereignty more broadly.

The stakes are clear. When research outputs are hosted on platforms governed by foreign institutions or commercial interests, a distant political decision or a change in business model can sever access overnight with no warning and no remedy. Repositories, properly resourced and interconnected, offer something different: a durable, locally governed foundation on which genuine research sovereignty can be built. The momentum is there. What is needed now is the commitment to match it.

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